

Trends in shrimp shells valorization for bioactive ingredients extraction: Opinion and perspectives towards circular biorefinery approaches

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ABSTRACT

The valorization of shrimp shells (SS) has gained attention from various stakeholders due to its environmental benefits and its potential as a valuable source of chitin/chitosan, proteins, lipids, minerals. Conventional extraction of chitin/chitosan from SS has been controversially debated, prompting exploration into the feasibility of green technologies for SS valorization. This study reviews trends in SS valorization, highlights green technologies used, and compares them with conventional extraction methods based on research from the past five years. Conventional extraction of chitin/chitosan was reported to hinder the recovery of other bioactive compounds such as proteins and lipids. Alternative green technologies (including microbial fermentation, enzymatic processes, green solvent, and advanced physical techniques) show potential for eliminating the use of harsh chemicals such as hydrochloric acid and concentrated sodium hydroxide. However, the complexity of these technologies limits their application in industrial scale valorization. Both techniques (conventional and green technologies) produced wastewater as a side stream which obviously left another environmental issue to be solved. Considering the role of side stream valorization in achieving The United Nations sustainability goals, an effective, scalable circular biorefinery approach to SS valorization is urgently needed.

1. Introduction: shrimp shells valorization

Global shellfish consumption is reported to be rising each year, driven by its widespread availability and nutritional benefits. Consequently, this leads to the generation of significant amounts of side streams. For instance, approximately 5.6 million tons of shrimp are harvested annually, of which only 40% is edible, leaving around 60%—or nearly 3.4 million tons—as waste or side streams. The valorization of shellfish side streams, including shrimp shells, has become a significant concern in recent years due to the high volume and costs associated with its proper disposal (Ling Wen Xia et al., 2024; Venugopal et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2024). However, improper disposal negatively impact the environment and consequently society – a concern that has already been observed in several countries (Mathew et al., 2021b). The side streams from shrimp processing are generated at each stage of processing from post-harvesting to consumption stage (Eggink et al., 2025). In addition to the non-edible part composed of shells, heads, tails and known

collectively as shrimp shells (SS), the main side stream in shrimp processing is processing-wastewater (PW) which is generated in the washing, thawing and cooking steps. The whole shrimp processing from farming, harvesting, processing, and its side streams valorization is illustrated in Fig. 1. During shrimp processing, wastewater is generated from thawing, washing, and cooking, which is excluded from the current study. Shrimp farming also utilizes huge amounts of water as documented by (Iber and Kasan, 2021).

The valorization of the shrimp processing side streams including PW and SS has been extensively evaluated on account of the potential benefits in terms of nutrient recovery and in reducing negative environmental impacts (Eggink et al., 2025). The PW mainly contains dissolved protein, pigment, and lipids (Forghani et al., 2021). It might also contain salt depending on the cooking ingredients. The presence of dissolved protein and organic materials induces chemical oxygen demand (COD), biological oxygen demand (BOD), and pathogenic microorganisms. Nutrient recovery from PW can be conducted using different

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techniques including membrane filtration and/or pH precipitation (Tonon et al., 2016). This strategy will improve the wastewater quality to be discharged into the environment.

SS is a more complex material than PW, consisting of compounds which are strongly bound to each other. SS is dominated by chitin and protein (20 – 45%) and some minor compounds including pigment, lipid, enzymes, minerals and vitamins (De Aguiar Saldanha Pinheiro et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2024; Zou et al., 2021). The abundance of these nutrient compounds makes it more challenging because the end-target compounds vary depending on the research interests. In addition to that, the extraction of bioactive compounds from SS involves a high amount of water containing harsh acid, bases, and/or organic solvents which are harmful to the water and environment (Mathew et al., 2021b). The potential of nutrient recovery from SS has been reported frequently. Most of these studies are focused on extraction, application, and biological properties of bioactive compounds from shrimp shells. Although the recovery of bioactive compounds from SS as mentioned can be expected, there is little reported on the circular biorefinery approach to shrimp shell valorization.

Therefore, the current study discusses a potential circular biorefinery approach in valorizing side streams of shrimp processing. The main objectives of the current study specifically focus on the valorization of SS itself. Most studies conducted on shrimp shell valorization are related to chitin extraction and its conversion to chitosan due to its abundance in shrimp shells and its versatile application in biomaterials, pharmaceuticals, and food products. During the extraction of chitin, protein is isolated by sodium hydroxide, calcium carbonate is isolated by hydrochloric acid, and then chitin is converted into chitosan which requires strong alkalinity. These extraction steps generate a huge amount of water which usually contains high amounts of protein and minerals (Wani et al., 2023). Based on the most recent reported studies (2021 – 2025) on the valorization of SS, the possibilities of circular biorefinery of SS valorization can be achieved, thus providing a sustainable valorization process. Research gaps and future challenges in achieving a zero-waste approach for the shrimp processing industry are also highlighted.

2. Current trend in the valorization of shrimp shells

2.1. General trends of shrimp shell valorization

Six of the most-commonly consumed shrimp species worldwide include white leg shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*), giant tiger prawn (*Penaeus monodon*), giant river prawn (*Macrobrachium rosenbergii*), brown shrimp (*Crangon crangon L*), common prawn (*Palaemon serratus*) and common ditch shrimp (*Palaemon varians Leach*) (Rossi et al., 2024). The shrimp shells usually consist of head, tails, viscera, cephalothorax, and exoskeleton (Abuzar et al., 2023). Although the chemical structure of the shrimp shells is complex, the head part usually contains a higher amount of crude fat, while crude protein (total of nitrogen-containing protein and chitin) and ash (including minerals) are varied throughout the shell's part (Rossi et al., 2024). Chitin has been the most studied compound from shrimp shells. However, it has been emphasized that shrimp shells are also a good source of protein, minerals, and pigments. To date, the potential for valorization has been reported widely. Shrimp shells have been used in the development of food products including bread, crackers, fortified drinks, cheese, shell powder, seasoning powder, and sauce paste (Abuzar et al., 2023).

As mentioned earlier, shrimp shells are a complex material. Therefore, removing or recovering certain compounds is affected by the presence of others. Chitin seems to be the main component in the complex structure of shrimp shells. Minerals, protein, lipids, and pigments must be removed to obtain chitin. In other words, fractionation of those compounds can be continuously carried out during the chitin extraction. Initial steps include demineralization and deproteinization which can be done in reverse. Decolorization can also be carried out to obtain colorless chitin and chitosan. However, the crucial step is the demineralization and deproteinization stage to obtain chitin and deacetylation process to convert chitin to chitosan. Conventionally, demineralization is carried out by using strong acids (HCl), deproteinization is carried out using NaOH, and demineralization is carried out using high concentration of NaOH which is at least 40% (Pakizeh et al., 2021). In theory, from the demineralization and deproteinization stage,

Fig. 1. Processing of shrimp from farming to end-products including side streams generated during the shrimp processing.

minerals and protein can be obtained respectively. However, during the demineralization stage, protein can also be released from the shell's matrix thus it dissolves into the solvent. In each of those stages (demineralization, deproteinization, and deacetylation), it requires washing to neutralize the pH. This washing stage utilizes a high amount of water, between 5 and 10 times the initial volume of the solvent used during the process. Fig. 2 outlines that every 1 Kg of fresh shrimp shells used for chitosan extraction will generate at least 45 L of water (Naibaho et al., 2025). Although the value-added compounds can be obtained (mineral from demineralization water and protein from deproteinization water), the process generates a high amount of wastewater which can be harmful to the environment. In addition to that, each of the stages requires a high temperature to generate high quality end products. This aspect contributes to the high energy consumption during the process.

Bioprocessing, by employing microbes and enzyme technology, has potential for use in shrimp shell valorization (Venugopal, 2021; Zou et al., 2021), although it might not be feasible from an economical perspective due to the time requirement and the high cost of commercial enzymes. In addition to that, the purity of targeted compounds can be difficult to ensure due to the many factors affecting the microbes and enzymes efficiency including temperature control, time, substrates, and species (Zou et al., 2021). Sustainable advanced processing as well as the guidelines have also been utilized in the extraction of bioactive compounds from shrimp shells (De Aguiar Saldanha Pinheiro et al., 2021; Ling Wen Xia et al., 2024; Mathew et al., 2021b; Venugopal et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2024). It includes a biotechnological approach, green chemical, and advanced technologies; which is discussed separately in Section 2.2.

2.2. Trends in green valorization approach

Recently, the application of green and sustainable valorization of SS has been well summarized including biological extraction (microbial fermentation and enzymatic), green solvents, and advanced physical technologies (Mathew et al., 2020; Putra et al., 2024; Rossi et al., 2024; Wani et al., 2023). Fermentation by microbes follows the same aim as chemical processing, such as demineralization, deproteinization, and deacetylation. For demineralization, lactic acid producing bacteria such as *Lactobacillus plantarum* ATCC 14917 and *Bacillus subtilis* ATCC 6051 are often used. The presence of lactic acid will detach the minerals from the SS matrix. Deproteinization can be carried out by fermentation with protease-producing bacteria such as *Streptomyces sp* SCUT-3, *Paenibacillus mucilaginosus* TKU032, *Paenibacillus elgii* TKU051, and *Brevibacillus parabrevis* TKU046. Deproteinization by microbes is promoted by proteolytic enzymes secreted during microbial fermentation. During this step, other valuable compounds are also obtained such as proteases, prebiotics, and antioxidants. Occasionally, single fermentation can be carried out for demineralization and deproteinization at the same time, combining acid-and proteolytic-producing microbes (Mathew et al., 2020). Deacetylation uses chitinase-generating microbes in order to convert chitin to chitosan or microbes which have chitin-degrading activity. Enzymatic processing applies a similar concept, employing different proteases to remove proteins from the SS matrix. Green

solvents include natural deep eutectic solvent, electrochemical, and ionic liquid (Sixto-Berrocal et al., 2023; Tkaczewska et al., 2024). Advanced physical techniques have been widely reported not only in SS valorization, but in the valorization of food processing side streams in general. They include microwave, ultrasound, subcritical water extraction, supercritical fluid extraction, and pulse electric field (Putra et al., 2024; Rossi et al., 2024).

Advancing research in shrimp shell valorization for obtaining value-added products (minerals, protein, chitosan, and pigments) aims to reduce the chemical residues and the energy consumption with an expectation of designing a sustainable valorization process (Mathew et al., 2020; Putra et al., 2024; Rossi et al., 2024). However, this approach can be challenging in different aspects. For instance, biological processing is often carried out at a mild temperature ranging between 40 and 50 °C, and it requires long incubation times usually more than 7 days (Gao et al., 2024) and thus a demanding controlled process. Physical techniques promote a shorter processing time with a higher temperature exposure and potentially reduce the chemical exposures and/or chemical concentration (Gao et al., 2024; Putra et al., 2024).

Although conventional valorization of shrimp shells using harsh chemicals negatively affects the environment, newly adopted green methods such as fermentation, enzymatic processes, and advanced physical methods are also facing their own limitations. The major limitation is the reproducibility in industrial scale production. Microbial fermentation requires a long time process, high enzymatic process costs, and advanced physical methods still require different solvents (Mathew et al., 2020; Putra et al., 2024; Rossi et al., 2024). Microbial fermentation is affected by various factors including microbial strains, pH control, temperature, incubation period, media types and composition, ratios, and different specific microbe requirements (Gao et al., 2024). Physical techniques are often influenced by temperature and time exposures (Putra et al., 2024). Green solvents are currently very limited in the commercial market, and it is a complicated challenge to synthesize in laboratory scale (Gao et al., 2024; Putra et al., 2024). From the industrial point of view, a stable quality of end-products is desirable to match those achieved by conventional methods. Although some proposed green methods have generated high quality products with less chemical residue, a stable quality has yet to be guaranteed due to the challenges in production scale-up (Nirmal et al., 2020). It is certain that soon, more investigation into the industrial scale of the green technologies of SS valorization is still needed.

3. Circular biorefinery approach for shrimp shell valorization

The general valorization approach to SS is presented in Fig. 1. As mentioned above, the recovery of the bioactive compounds can be obtained depending on the extraction techniques and approaches. In the last five years, huge efforts have been made towards sustainable extraction by employing microbial, enzymes, green solvents, and/or advanced physical methods. This approach has also been reported and excellently summarized recently (Abuzar et al., 2023; Eggink et al., 2025; Nirmal et al., 2020; Putra et al., 2024; Rossi et al., 2024). The continued evaluation of shrimp shell valorization will provide a variety

Fig. 2. Conventional extraction of chitin from shrimp shells, its conversion to chitosan, and energy consumption as well as side streams generated during the chitosan extraction (*estimated if the washing process generates 10x volume wastewater).

of valorization routes which can be applied depending on their suitability and the specific interest or required output of different stakeholders. However, investigation on the utilization of the whole SS demonstrating the zero-waste valorization concept is very limited. Most of the studies report on single compound extraction through the application of different techniques, which makes it difficult to comprehend the circular biorefinery strategy.

The extraction methods for different compounds can vary, as mentioned earlier. Protein, pigments, lipids, and minerals can be obtained during the stages of chitin extraction, regardless of the techniques applied. Recent trends are towards minimizing harsh chemical and energy consumption during the extraction. Optimum conditions for the yield recovery is affected by internal and external factors. Internal factors include the source of the SS, particle size, moisture ratio, and complexity of the structure. External factors include solvents used, application techniques, solvent ratios, reaction/incubation times, and purification methods. However, a sustainable and circular biorefinery approach has never been deeply examined. For example, almost all the compounds obtained from SS generate wastewater as a side stream during the extraction process, regardless of the extraction techniques. Conventional extraction generates strong alkaline and acidic wastewater; enzymatic and microbial techniques generate mineral- and nitrogen-containing wastewater which induce a rise in BOD and COD. This issue has never been addressed and thus the need for a circular biorefinery approach is urgent, in addition to the sustainable extraction of these bioactive compounds.

3.1. Single compound extraction

3.1.1. Chitin and/or chitosan

Chitin and/or chitosan has been the most investigated compound due to its abundance (up to 30% (dry basis) in SS. Chitin is obtained by removing protein and calcium carbonate which is conventionally done by sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid, respectively. After that, the chitin is converted to chitosan through a deacetylation reaction using concentrated alkaline (Dong et al., 2024). Chitin polymer consists of a linear chain of 1-4 linked 2-acetamido-2-deoxy-b-D-glucopyranose units and chitosan consists of one primary amino and 2 free hydroxyl groups in every C6 unit (Abuzar et al., 2023; Gao et al., 2024; Nirmal et al., 2020; Rossi et al., 2024; Wani et al., 2023). Chitosan has a linear chain of GlcN units linked together by b-1,4 glycosidic bonds. Unlike chitin, chitosan contains a higher percentage of free amino groups due to the deacetylation process. Thus the chitosan is more positively charged making it more soluble in acidic solution and allowing it to form complexes such as DNA, proteins, and polysaccharides (Gao et al., 2024; Wani et al., 2023). The interest in chitin and/or chitosan extraction from SS is due to its natural bioactivity, biocompatible, biodegradability, and non-toxic properties. The primary constituent of chitosan is glucosamine, a naturally occurring substance synthesized within the body from glucose. Glucosamine plays an important role in the formation of glycosaminoglycan, a key component in the formation of cartilage tissue (Rossi et al., 2024).

Chitin and/or chitosan extraction has been evaluated widely both in conventional or advanced techniques. Conventional chitosan extraction including the basic requirement and the output of the extraction process is presented in Fig. 2. Conventional methods continue to be used although they employ HCl in demineralization, NaOH in deproteinization, H₂O₂ in decolorization, and highly concentrated NaOH in deacetylation, which have demonstrated disadvantages (Dinculescu et al., 2024; Eddy et al., 2020; Hosney et al., 2024; Rahman and Maniruzzaman, 2023; Said Al Hoqani et al., 2020). This phenomenon might be due to the simplicity of the process, ease of control, and the higher possibility of generating a standardized chitosan thus more acceptable from an industrial point of view. However, as we are facing a global climate crisis, the utilization of chemicals in chitosan extraction must be re-considered to reduce the environmental impact. These referenced

studies did not include an investigation into the wastewater generated during the chitin and chitosan extraction, which makes the outputs less relevant considering the current global issue. In addition to that, conventional extraction is often carried out at certain temperatures and reaction times of up to 100 °C and 6 h, respectively. Modifying the process to reduce reaction time and/or temperature will also reduce the energy consumption during the extraction process.

Chemical extraction can be modified by combining enzymatic and/or advanced physical techniques and therefore reducing the utilization of harsh chemicals. Demineralization was investigated to replace HCl by utilizing citric acid (Matouri et al., 2024; Pérez et al., 2022; Pohling et al., 2022). From an environmental impact, citric acid is a safe and cost-effective alternative. However, the utilization of citric acid requires multiple steps and high concentrations of citric acid which consequently require higher energy consumption. In addition to that, citric acid will form viscous side streams thus might make it difficult to handle the side streams after the demineralization process. Elimination of NaOH in deproteinization has been evaluated by enzymatic processes using bromelain, papain, neutral protease, trypsin, and alkaline protease (Dong et al., 2023; Pérez et al., 2022). Advanced physical techniques by a subsequent process of ultrasonication and subcritical water were employed at the deproteinization stage (Matouri et al., 2024). Ultrasound-assisted extraction was able to shorten the extraction time from several hours in conventional methods to only 30 min during the demineralization and deproteinization (Naibaho et al., 2025). Demineralization and deproteinization was carried out in a single fermentation with *Paenibacillus jamilae* BAT1 (Taser et al., 2021). This fermentation process eliminates chemicals although the deacetylation process was conducted by NaOH 12.5M. Modification of deacetylation aiming to eliminate and/or reduce it has also been very scarcely reported. Microwave-assisted deacetylation was evaluated (Dong et al., 2023). Although it reduced the reaction time to 5 min, it was carried out by NaOH 50% at a very high ratio (1:25) and the process was repeated three times. This step might have reduced the reaction time but not the amount of concentrated NaOH. A complete elimination of chemicals in chitosan extraction has been investigated using an enzymatic process (Deng et al., 2020) and a fermentation process (Sixto-Berrocal et al., 2023). In terms of the fermentation process, oftentimes it requires a long incubation period which is not only time consuming but also energy consuming in controlling the temperature depending on the optimum condition of the microbes used. Decolorization is usually carried out after protein and minerals are removed. However, the modification in the decolorization has never been specifically investigated although it could be done by lipid extraction which can be modified by other techniques which will be discussed further.

3.1.2. Protein and derivatives

Proteins are involved in the structure, function, and regulation of cells and tissues. Protein as well as minerals can be obtained as a step prior to the chitin extraction. Protein is isolated by sodium hydroxide and calcium carbonate is isolated by hydrochloric acid (Wani et al., 2023). Although NaOH is used at the deproteinization stage of chitin extraction, it is not preferred to use NaOH for protein extraction, although it might have been used in a small amount to adjust the pH and achieve alkaline conditions. The use of proteolytic bacteria in fermentation of SS was reported and the filtrate was collected as a bioactive hydrolysate (Mechri et al., 2020). Enzymatic extraction was carried out by employing Alcalase and Flavourzyme to dissolve and hydrolyze protein from SS (Leiva-Portilla et al., 2023). Recently, ultrafine grinding and electrostatic separation were evaluated to increase the protein content and enhance the protein properties (Tian et al., 2025). Another protein derivative from SS is gelatin which was obtained after partial hydrolysis of collagen (Charoenkool et al., 2024). The solid fractions from those studies were the chitin which was not investigated. Although these documented strategies might not be able to recover the whole protein from SS, it might allow the recovery of some of the protein

before the exposure of harsh chemicals in chitin extraction.

3.1.3. Lipids and derivatives

Lipid fractions from shrimp contain carotenoids and fatty acids. Carotenoid exists as β -carotene and/or astaxanthin and its esters. It contains 40 carbon atoms conjugated with double bonds and forms lipid-soluble tetraterpenoids. Astaxanthin, the most studied in shrimp, conjugates with a chemical complex with proteins as caroteno-proteins or lipoprotein as caroteno-lipoproteins. SS contains a higher total lipid content compared to that of the shrimp meat because most lipids are in the head part of the shrimp which is often not consumed (Dayakar et al., 2022; Gulzar et al., 2020; Pattanaik et al., 2020). Lipids of shrimp shells are composed of fatty acids, carotenoids, polar lipids, and fat-soluble vitamins. Carotenoid is a fat-soluble pigment which is often associated with protein as caroteno-proteins. Therefore, the extraction of caroteno-proteins was carried out utilizing papain as a proteolytic enzyme (Dayakar et al., 2022; Pattanaik et al., 2020). The supernatant is collected after incubation for precipitation (Pattanaik et al., 2020) or spray drying (Dayakar et al., 2022). Astaxanthin is one of the pigments which contributes to the red-yellow color in shrimp shells. It has 10 times the antioxidant effect of other carotenoids, 100 times the effect of α -tocopherol, and 1000 times that of coenzyme Q10. Discussions on the extraction of lipids have been well presented, as well as the potential application of lipids from shrimp shells (Gulzar et al., 2020). The investigation of lipids and their derivatives from SS is very limited due to their sensitivity to certain conditions during the extraction process, including light exposure, temperature, and solvents. Ethanol and acetone at different concentrations and ratios were evaluated to extract carotenoids and astaxanthin from SS (Maia et al., 2023). A combination of ultrasound and subcritical water extraction using different solvents (citric acid, water, ethanol, or methanol) was also evaluated for carotenoid recovery (Moreira et al., 2023). There is no clear recommendation with regard to the order of the extraction process to facilitate a zero-waste concept, or at which stage the lipid extraction should be carried out. This is crucial information as the lipid components in SS are very sensitive to oxidation thus damaging its biological properties (Gulzar et al., 2020; Pattanaik et al., 2020; Rossi et al., 2024).

3.2. Multiple compounds extraction

Single fermentation of SS was applied to obtain protein in supernatant and chitin in the precipitate (Canpulat et al., 2024; Mathew et al., 2021a). Fermentation processes were also employed on SS with three different strains including *Lactobacillus plantarum* LV33204, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* LV2122 (strong proteolytic activity), and *Aeromonas dhakensis* LV1111 (chitin-degrading activity). After fermentation, the supernatant was collected for peptide identification while the precipitate was used for astaxanthin and phenolic extraction (Huang et al., 2022). The same approach was conducted utilizing enzymes to hydrolyze the protein and fractionate the lipid fractions (Tkaczewska et al., 2024). These methods were able to detach the protein from the complex structure of SS without chemicals involved. Since there was no demineralization step, the dissolution of minerals from SS might occur thus requiring further purification for a higher protein purity. In terms of chitin purification, a washing procedure is required to remove impurities which can be protein, minerals, and microbial cells. These impurities without further treatment can increase the BOD and COD of the effluents.

Multiple steps of enzymatic extraction generated three different end-products including protein from the first protease incubation, chitin hydrolysate from the chitinase incubation, and astaxanthin from the final extraction from the solid residue (Deng et al., 2020). An alternative process was carried out to obtain astaxanthin resulting in an oil fraction at the initial stage using superfluid critical extraction, followed by protein fractionation by mechanical squeezing, and finally chitin extraction by conventional methods using NaOH and HCl (Aneesh et al.,

2023). Peptides, chitin, and astaxanthin were fractionated combining mechanochemical methods and enzymes including neutral protease, acid protease, keratinase, bromelain, papain, alkaline protease, and compound proteases (Su et al., 2023). After SS was incubated with enzymes at a certain ratio, it was mixed with oil in zirconia balls for mechanochemical reactions. From these steps, end products were separated into an astaxanthin layer, small peptide amino acids aqueous layer, and solid residue (Su et al., 2023). These are the examples of the strategies for zero-waste concept valorization that have progressed in the last five years. Although some of the studies did not fully consider the generated wastewater during the purification and/or extraction, this will need to be urgently addressed soon to achieve a circular biorefinery approach for shrimp shell valorization.

4. Research gaps, perspectives, and future challenges

As the extraction approach is modified, the input and output illustrated in Fig. 2 will be different. For instance, microbial fermentation, which could take up to 3 days at controlled temperatures (Gao et al., 2024), does not require solvents. However, it will require energy for controlling inoculation and incubation temperatures for days. The output of microbial fermentation would be a supernatant containing an end-product without chemical residue; however it might contain impurities such as minerals and microbial cells. A circular biorefinery concept could be achieved by considering a zero-waste concept from the SS as well as from the side streams during extraction processes. It was highlighted that traditional SS valorization should be an expensive process, destructive, and wasteful (Wani et al., 2023) although it was supposed to be cheap, resulting in less or no waste, and avoiding environmental damage. SS is a serious source of pollutants because of its low decomposition rate, and its decomposition causes water acidification (Pakizeh et al., 2021). Selection of chemical, technical guidance, and step processing have been well established in terms of conventional chemical extraction of bioactive components from SS (Pakizeh et al., 2021). In addition to that, newly adopted sustainable and green technologies have also been presented recently (Mathew et al., 2020; Putra et al., 2024; Rossi et al., 2024; Wani et al., 2023) as discussed in Section 2.2. Considering the zero-waste valorization concept, all the above-mentioned bioactive compounds can be obtained from SS by considering the stability of each compound to specific conditions during extraction. For instance, pigments (carotenoid and or astaxanthin) are less resistant to light and temperature compared to other compounds. Removing minerals at low temperatures through acidic conditions could allow a higher pigment recovery before protein extraction.

To date, no investigation has been carried out on the wastewater generated during SS valorization. Fig. 2 illustrates the extraction of chitosan from 1 Kg of fresh SS illustrated with minimum molarity and solvent ratio. If the ratio of SS and solvent used at 1:10 and the required water in washing step to neutralize the pH is at least ten times that of the initial solvent used, the conventional extractions will generate around 10L of 0.1M HCl (rich in minerals), 5.2L 0.1M NaOH (rich in protein), and 5L NaOH 4%. Some studies utilized solvents at a higher concentration and higher ratio. This will generate a higher volume of wastewater to extract 40g chitosan from 1 Kg of SS. The pH of the wastewater obtained from demineralization, deproteinization, and deacetylation is about 2.0, 12.0, and 13.6 respectively (unpublished data). Mixing these three different waters did not produce a neutral pH due to the strong alkaline in the deacetylation process (unpublished data). Further investigation should be carried out for further justification of this wastewater. In addition to that, shrimp shells are usually washed with water prior to drying and extraction; several studies used acid (citric or HCl) in pretreatment as a washing step. These wastewaters might be useful to adjust the salinity or pH of the wastewater from chitosan extraction.

The combination of discussed methods (biological process, physical techniques, and/or green solvents) might be worthy of investigation in

terms of their impact on the quality parameters of wastewater generated during the extraction. The presence of residual nitrogen, minerals, and other unrecovered bioactive compounds in these wastewaters might open the possibility for aquatic plant cultivation. The mixture of these wastewaters might contain high amounts of salt from NaOH and HCl which is widely tolerated in duckweed cultivation (Ujong et al., 2025). In terms of nutrient recovery during the chitin extraction, proteins and pigments might need to be isolated in a gentle process before it undergoes further chitin extraction. It is obvious that the extraction cannot fully isolate the target components. Therefore, the remaining nutrient in the SS matrix further goes to harsh chemical reactions as a nutrient stock for aquatic plant cultivation.

All the reported techniques in SS valorization have their own advantages and disadvantages in terms of yield recovery, end-product properties, and side streams generated during the extraction. Differences in applied methods can vary depending on the researcher's personal interests, resource availability, and experience. A circular biorefinery approach in SS valorization must be taken seriously due to its urgency in terms of generating bioactive compounds and new materials as well as reducing the harmful effects to the environment whether it is valorized or not. SS valorization is supposed to reduce the harmful effect. Therefore, the generated side streams during the valorization should be avoided. The circular biorefinery approach of SS as emphasized in this work would support achieving the sustainable development goals by The United Nations such as zero hunger, good health and well-being, clean water and sanitation, industry, innovation and infrastructure, sustainable cities and communities, responsible consumption and production, climate action, life below water, and life on land.

5. Concluding remarks

Shrimp shells represent one of the most abundant and underutilized marine processing side streams, with significant potential as a sustainable source of chitin/chitosan, proteins, lipids, pigments, and minerals. This review highlights that while conventional chemical extraction methods remain dominant due to their simplicity and reproducibility, they are associated with substantial environmental burdens, particularly high chemical consumption, energy demand, and the generation of large volumes of untreated wastewater. These drawbacks undermine the very objective of shrimp shell valorization as an environmentally responsible strategy. Recent advances in green technologies including microbial fermentation, enzymatic processing, green solvents, and advanced physical techniques, demonstrate promising alternatives for reducing chemical inputs and improving the sustainability of shrimp shell valorization. However, despite their technical potential, these approaches face major challenges related to process complexity, long processing times, high costs, limited availability of green solvents, and difficulties in scaling up while maintaining consistent product quality. Consequently, most studies remain focused on single-compound recovery rather than integrated utilization of the whole shrimp shell matrix.

A critical gap identified in the current literature is the lack of attention given to the side streams generated during extraction processes, particularly wastewater rich in organic matter, minerals, and residual bioactive compounds. Regardless of whether conventional or green extraction methods are employed, wastewater generation remains unavoidable and represents a significant environmental concern that has not been sufficiently addressed. This oversight highlights the urgent need to shift research efforts toward a holistic circular biorefinery framework that integrates compound recovery with side-stream management and nutrient recycling. Future research should prioritize the development of scalable, integrated valorization strategies that consider the sequential recovery of sensitive compounds, minimize energy and chemical inputs, and incorporate wastewater treatment or reuse as part of the overall process design. Approaches such as combining biological, physical, and mild chemical methods, as well as exploring the reuse of

nutrient-rich effluents for applications such as aquatic plant cultivation, could significantly enhance the sustainability of shrimp shell valorization. In conclusion, achieving a truly circular biorefinery approach for shrimp shell valorization requires moving beyond isolated extraction techniques toward system-level solutions that balance product yield, environmental impact, and industrial feasibility. Addressing these challenges will not only reduce the environmental footprint of the shrimp processing industry but also contribute meaningfully to global sustainability goals, including responsible consumption and production, clean water and sanitation, climate action, and the protection of aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Joncer Naibaho: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Harikrishnan Manikyparambil:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Shay Hannon:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Shivani Pathania:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration. **Ciara McDonagh:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Software, Project administration. **Brijesh K. Tiwari:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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